

HYGROTHERMALLY STABLE ASYMMETRIC COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH OPTIMAL COUPLING OF DEFORMATION MODES

R. Haynes^{1*}, E. Armanios²

¹ Vehicle Technology Directorate, Army Research Laboratory, Aberdeen Proving Ground, MD,

² Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, University of Texas at Arlington, Arlington, TX

* Corresponding author (robert.a.haynes43.civ@mail.mil)

Keywords: *hygrothermal stability, asymmetric stacking sequences, coupling*

1 Introduction

Composite laminates made from multiple plies of unidirectional fibers in a matrix have the potential for tailoring of their response to produce coupling between deformation modes not achievable in conventional materials [1]. For example, a flat laminate can experience extension-twist coupling when using an angle-ply stacking sequence, that is, $[\pm\theta]$. In the past, designers of structures made from composite laminates have often taken a conservative approach whereby special stacking sequences are used to produce a quasi-isotropic laminate. Further, designers have often restricted themselves to symmetric laminates whenever possible to eliminate hygrothermal instabilities, i.e. out-of-plane warping due to temperature or moisture changes [2]. Such restrictions on stacking sequence can lead to either suboptimal configurations, which could increase weight and decrease performance, or suppression of a potentially advantageous deformation mode. For example, an asymmetric stacking sequence is necessary to achieve extension-twist coupling and so restriction to symmetric stacking sequences will eliminate the possibility of extension-twist coupling.

This work first presents the bounds on hygrothermally stable asymmetric laminates, and then second, explores the potential of hygrothermally stable laminates to perform at levels near that of unconstrained laminates. Performance is measured as the achievable level of coupling based on the linear compliance coefficient. Couplings investigated in this work include

extension-twist, bend-twist, shear-twist, extension-bend, and anticlastic.

2 Hygrothermally Stable Asymmetric Laminates

For laminates constructed from identical plies, two necessary and sufficient conditions for hygrothermal stability have been derived in previous work [3], given as either

$$N_{xx}^{(T,H)} = N_{yy}^{(T,H)} \quad (1)$$

$$N_{xy}^{(T,H)} = M_{xx}^{(T,H)} = M_{yy}^{(T,H)} = M_{xy}^{(T,H)} = 0$$

or

$$B_{ij} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where $N_{ij}^{(T,H)}$ and $M_{ij}^{(T,H)}$ are the non-mechanical in-plane and out-of-plane force and moment resultants, respectively, as derived in Classical Lamination Theory [1], and B_{ij} represents coupling stiffness coefficients between in-plane and out-of-plane deformation modes. Equations 1 and 2 can be recast solely in term of the fiber orientation angle, θ , and each ply's location in the stacking sequence as [3]

$$\sum_{k=1}^n k \cos 2\theta_k = 0$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n k \sin 2\theta_k = 0$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \cos 2\theta_k = 0 \quad (3a-d)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \sin 2\theta_k = 0$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^n (2k-n-1) \cos 2\theta_k &= 0 \\ \sum_{k=1}^n (2k-n-1) \sin 2\theta_k &= 0 \\ \sum_{k=1}^n (2k-n-1) \cos 4\theta_k &= 0 \\ \sum_{k=1}^n (2k-n-1) \sin 4\theta_k &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4a-d)$$

respectively, where n is the number of plies.

Equation 1 allows for coupling between in-plane and out-of-plane deformation modes, while Equation 2 does not allow for coupling between in-plane and out-of-plane deformation modes. Both Equation 1 and 2 can be satisfied using either a symmetric or asymmetric stacking sequence. Therefore, either condition for hygrothermal stability can be used to find hygrothermally stable asymmetric stacking sequences and produce stacking sequences with coupling between out-of-plane deformation modes, but only Equation 1 can be used to produce stacking sequences with coupling between in-plane and out-of-plane deformation modes.

A minimum of five plies is required to achieve a hygrothermally stable asymmetric laminate [3]. Only one unique five-ply stacking sequence exists that is hygrothermally stable, given by

$$[76.3 / -33.6 / 0 / 33.6 / -76.3] \quad (5)$$

which is hygrothermally stable by Equation 1. For six or more plies, multiple asymmetric stacking sequences can be found that are hygrothermally stable by either Equation 1 or 2. An example of a six-ply asymmetric stacking sequence that is hygrothermally stable by Equation 2 is

$$[6.2^\circ / -20.1^\circ / 30^\circ / -30^\circ / 20.1^\circ / -6.2^\circ] \quad (6)$$

Families of laminates that satisfy the condition for hygrothermal stability exist for six or more plies and seven or more plies for the conditions in Equations 1 and 2, respectively. An example of a

laminate family that meets the hygrothermal stability condition in Equation 1 is

$$[\theta / \theta-90 / \theta-60 / \theta+30 / \theta+60 / \theta-30] \quad (7)$$

and an example of a laminate family that meets the hygrothermal stability condition in Equation 2 is

$$[\theta_1 / \theta_2 / \theta_2 / \theta_3 / \theta_1 / \theta_1 / \theta_2] \quad (8)$$

A more complete list of asymmetric hygrothermally stable laminate families is provided in [4].

3 Optimization of Coupling of Deformation Modes

In order to explore the achievable performance of coupled laminates, a constrained optimization routine is used. For this work, the objective function is derived from the inverse of the linear constitutive law as given in Classical Lamination Theory [1] without considering non-mechanical loading, as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \kappa_{xx} \\ \kappa_{yy} \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{11} & \alpha_{12} & \alpha_{16} & \beta_{11} & \beta_{12} & \beta_{16} \\ \alpha_{12} & \alpha_{22} & \alpha_{26} & \beta_{21} & \beta_{22} & \beta_{26} \\ \alpha_{16} & \alpha_{26} & \alpha_{66} & \beta_{61} & \beta_{62} & \beta_{66} \\ \beta_{11} & \beta_{21} & \beta_{61} & \delta_{11} & \delta_{12} & \delta_{16} \\ \beta_{12} & \beta_{22} & \beta_{62} & \delta_{12} & \delta_{22} & \delta_{26} \\ \beta_{16} & \beta_{26} & \beta_{66} & \delta_{16} & \delta_{26} & \delta_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \\ M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where the in-plane and out-of-plane force and moment resultants are as defined previously and ε_{xx} , ε_{yy} , γ_{xy} , κ_{xx} , κ_{yy} , and κ_{xy} are the strains and curvatures. The compliance matrix is calculated from the inverse of the stiffness matrix, wherein the stiffness coefficients are given as

$$\begin{aligned} A_{ij} &= \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{Q}_{ij(k)} (h_k - h_{k-1}) \\ B_{ij} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{Q}_{ij(k)} (h_k^2 - h_{k-1}^2) \\ D_{ij} &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{Q}_{ij(k)} (h_k^3 - h_{k-1}^3) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{Q}_{ij(k)}$ and h_k represent the transformed reduced stiffness coefficients and height

relative to the laminate midplane for the k^{th} ply, respectively.

It can be shown that the parameter that governs the twist response due to an applied axial force is either β_{16} or β_{26} depending on whether the force is acting on the surface normal to the x -direction or the y -direction, respectively; in this work only β_{16} is investigated. The parameter that governs the twist response due to an applied bending is either δ_{16} or δ_{26} depending on whether the bending moment is acting on the surface normal to the x -direction or the y -direction, respectively; in this work only δ_{16} is investigated. The parameter that governs the twist response due to an applied in-plane shear is β_{66} . The parameter that governs the primary bending response due to an applied axial force is either β_{11} or β_{22} depending on whether the force is acting on the surface normal to the x -direction or the y -direction, respectively; in this work only β_{11} is investigated. The parameter that governs the secondary bending response due to an applied axial force is β_{12} or β_{21} depending on whether the force is acting on the surface normal to the x -direction or the y -direction, respectively; in this work only β_{12} is investigated. Finally, the response that governs the bending along an axis transverse to the axis normal to the surface on which the bending moment is acting (i.e. anticlastic curvature) due to that bending moment is δ_{12} .

The optimization is performed numerically using the Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) [5] implementation in MATLAB 7TM's `fmincon` function. The optimization finds a local minimum of the objective function, and as such in order to maximize the coupling, the objective function was taken to be

$$g(\{\theta_k : k = 1 \dots n\}) = -\{\beta, \delta\}_{ij}^2 \quad (11)$$

Since only local minima are identified, 10,000 random initial guesses that sufficiently cover the range of possible solutions were used. In all cases, the stacking sequence with the highest level of coupling was returned several times, providing confidence that it is in fact globally optimal.

The material properties of a T300/976 graphite/epoxy material system were used to

calculate the compliance coefficients. The elastic properties are provided in Table 1. For the constraints on hygrothermal stability, the relations in either Equation (3) or (4) are used as inputs to `fmincon`. The output of the optimization routine is the stacking sequence that produces the locally optimal coupling corresponding to the specific initial guess, subject to any applicable constraints.

3 Results

The optimization was run for extension-twist, bend-twist, shear-twist, extension-bend, and anticlastic coupling, each with and without constraint to hygrothermal stability.

3.1 Extension-twist Coupling

The results of the optimization of extension-twist coupling under both no constraint and constrained to hygrothermal stability by Equation 1 are provided in Table 2. Note that as mentioned above, the minimum number of plies needed for an asymmetric hygrothermally stable laminate is five. Also included in Table 2 is the percent reduction in coupling as a result of constraining to hygrothermal stability, measured as the difference in the compliance coefficients divided by the unconstrained compliance coefficient. Constraint to hygrothermal stability by Equation 2 will produce no coupling of in-plane and out-of-plane deformation modes, so this optimization was not performed.

3.2 Bend-twist Coupling

The results of the optimization of bend-twist coupling under constraint to hygrothermal stability by both Equations 1 and 2 are provided in Table 3. The unconstrained optimal bend-twist coupled stacking sequences are provided in Table 4 along with the percent reduction in coupling as a result of constraining to hygrothermal stability, measured as the difference in the compliance coefficients divided by the unconstrained compliance coefficient. The unconstrained laminates are also hygrothermally stable by Equation 2 and symmetric, except the seven- and eight-ply laminates, which have a negligible improvement in coupling over the laminate that is hygrothermally stable by Equation 2 with the same number of plies.

3.3 Shear-twist Coupling

The results of the optimization of shear-twist coupling under no constraints and constraint to hygrothermal stability by Equation 1 are provided in Table 5. Note that as mentioned above, the minimum number of plies needed for an asymmetric hygrothermally stable laminate is five. Also included in Table 5 is the percent reduction in coupling as a result of constraining to hygrothermal stability, measured as the difference in the compliance coefficients divided by the unconstrained compliance coefficient. Constraint to hygrothermal stability by Equation 2 will produce no coupling of in-plane and out-of-plane deformation modes, so this optimization was not performed.

3.4 Extension-bend Coupling; Primary Bending

The results of the optimization of extension-bend coupling, where the bending occurs along the same axis that the loading is applied, under no constraints and constraint to hygrothermal stability by Equation 1, are provided in Table 6. Note that as mentioned above, the minimum number of plies needed for an asymmetric hygrothermally stable laminate is five. Also included in Table 6 is the percent reduction in coupling as a result of constraining to hygrothermal stability, measured as the difference in the compliance coefficients divided by the unconstrained compliance coefficient. Constraint to hygrothermal stability by Equation 2 will produce no coupling of in-plane and out-of-plane deformation modes, so this optimization was not performed.

3.5 Extension-bend Coupling; Secondary Bending

The results of the optimization of extension-bend coupling, where the bending occurs along an orthogonal axis to that which the loading is applied, under no constraints and constraint to hygrothermal stability by Equation 1, are provided in Table 7. Note that as mentioned above, the minimum number of plies needed for an asymmetric hygrothermally stable laminate is five. Also included in Table 7 is the percent reduction in coupling as a result of constraining to hygrothermal stability, measured as the difference in the compliance coefficients divided by the

unconstrained compliance coefficient. Constraint to hygrothermal stability by Equation 2 will produce no coupling of in-plane and out-of-plane deformation modes, so optimizations under these conditions were not performed.

3.6 Anticlastic Coupling

The results of the optimization of anticlastic coupling under constraint to hygrothermal stability by both Equations 1 and 2 are provided in Table 8. The unconstrained optimal anticlastic coupled stacking sequences are provided in Table 9 along with the percent reduction in coupling as a result of constraining to hygrothermal stability, measured as the difference in the compliance coefficients divided by the unconstrained compliance coefficient.

4 Discussion

For most couplings, the loss in coupling due to the enforcement of hygrothermal stability reduces with increasing number of plies, which is likely due to the additional degrees of freedom associated with more plies. For both bend-twist and anticlastic coupling, constraint to hygrothermal stability by Equation 2 results in less loss of coupling than constraint to hygrothermal stability by Equation 1 for a given number of plies; in the case of bend-twist coupling there is a negligible loss in coupling when constrained to hygrothermal stability by Equation 2 for two through ten plies.

5 Conclusion

This work demonstrates that there are two conditions that can enforce hygrothermal stability, both of which can be achieved with asymmetric stacking sequences but only one that can produce non-zero coupling between in-plane and out-of-plane deformation modes. An optimization was performed to identify the laminates that produce the highest level of coupling for extension-twist, bend-twist, shear-twist, extension-twist, and anticlastic couplings, each subject to both no constraints and constraint to hygrothermal stability. It was found that having more plies often reduces the loss of coupling when the laminate is constrained to be hygrothermally stable.

References

- [1] R. M. Jones “*Mechanics of Composite Materials*”. 2nd edition, Taylor & Francis, Philadelphia, PA, 1999, pp. 190-203.
- [2] Z. Gürdal, R.T. Haftka and P. Hajela “*Design and Optimization of Laminated Composite Materials*”. John Wiley & Sons, New York, NY, 1999.
- [3] R. J. Cross, R. A. Haynes and E. A. Armanios “Families of Hygrothermally Stable Asymmetric Laminated Composites”. *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 42, No. 7, pp 697-716, 2008.
- [4] R. A. Haynes “Hygrothermally Stable Laminated Composites With Optimal Coupling”. PhD Dissertation, Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, GA, 2007.
- [5] P. E. Gill, W. Murray, and M. H. Wright, *Practical Optimization*, Academic Press, London, UK, 1981.

Table 1. Elastic properties of T300/976 graphite/epoxy material system.

Property	Value
E_{xx}	125 GPa
E_{yy}	8.45 GPa
G_{xy}	4.3 GPa
ν_{xy}	0.328
thickness	0.152 mm

Table 2. Unconstrained and Hygrothermally Stable Optimal Extension-twist Coupled Laminates

n	Unconstrained (°)	Hygrothermally Stable by Equation 1 (°)	% Reduction in Coupling compared to Unconstrained
2	[±24.7]	N/A	N/A
3	[-30.1 / 90.0 / 30.1]	N/A	N/A
4	[28.5 / -89.5 / 89.5 / -28.5]	N/A	N/A
5	[-27.7 / 90.0 / -90.0 / -90.0 / 27.7]	[-58.7 / 11.4 / 45 / 78.6 / -31.3]	52%
6	[-26.1 / -38.6 / 88.6 / -88.6 / 38.6 / 26.1]	[21.2 / -63.8 / -48.7 / 48.7 / 63.8 / -21.2]	37%
7	[-25.8 / -35.4 / 89.7 / 90 / -89.7 / 35.4 / 25.8]	[14.1 / -76.9 / -73.9 / 45 / -16.1 / -13.2 / 75.7]	47%
8	[-25.6 / -33.4 / 89.9 / 89.8 / -89.8 / -89.9 / 33.4 / 25.6]	[-21.5 / 72.1 / 57.9 / -29.6 / 29.6 / -57.9 / -72.1 / 21.5]	46%
9	[24.8 / 31.3 / 42.0 / -89.2 / 90 / 89.2 / -42.0 / -31.3 / -24.8]	[25.5 / -79 / 32.5 / -62.9 / 49.9 / 27.4 / 57 / -10.6 / 64.9]	40%
10	[24.7 / 30.4 / 39.0 / -89.5 / -89.2 / 89.2 / 89.5 / -39.0 / 30.4 / -24.7]	[16.2 / -69.0 / -65.3 / 31.8 / 42.1 / -42.1 / -31.8 / 65.3 / 69.0 / -16.2]	35%

Table 3. Hygrothermally Stable Optimal Bend-twist Coupled Laminates

n	Equation 1 (°)	Equation 2 (°)
2	N/A	[30.5] ₂
3	N/A	[-31.6 / 87.8] _s
4	[-24.3 / 65.7] _s	[32.8 / -88.2] _s
5	[27.8 / -76.7 / -24.4] _s	[33.3 / -88.4 / 33.3] _s
6	[-87.0 / -18.0 / 3.2 / 51.1 / 72.4 / -38.6]	[33.5 / -88.5 / 33.5] _s
7	[-26.6 / 76.7 / 70.5 / 24.4 / -21.9 / -27.8 / 75.4]	[33.6 / -88.5 / 33.6 / -88.5] _s
8	[25.6 / 23.0 / -67.0 / -64.4] _s	[-32.8 ₂ / 88.2 ₂] _s
9	[26.7 / 26.1 / -74.6 / -66.9 / -23.2] _s	[-33.1 ₂ / 88.4 ₅ / -33.1 ₂] _s
10	[-28.2 / -27.8 / 78.0 / 75.0 / 24.3] _s	[-33.3 ₂ / 88.4 ₂ / -33.3] _s

Table 4. Unconstrained Optimal Bend-twist Coupled Laminates with Coupling Loss due to Hygrothermal Stability

n	Stacking Sequence (°)	Equation 1 Coupling Loss	Equation 2 Coupling Loss
2	[30.5] ₂	N/A	0.00%
3	[-31.6 / 87.8] _s	N/A	0.00%
4	[32.8 / -88.2] _s	22.7%	0.00%
5	[33.3 / -88.4 / 33.3] _s	14.7%	0.00%
6	[33.5 / -88.5 / 33.5] _s	27.9%	0.00%
7	[33.2 / -88.4 / 33.4 / -88.5 / -88.4 / 33.0] ₂	18.6%	0.23%
8	[-33.3 / -33.2 / 88.4 / 88.5 / -33.5 / -33.4 / 88.4 / -33.3]	21.9%	0.17%
9	[-33.1] ₂ / 88.4] ₅ / -33.1] ₂	15.1%	0.00%
10	[-33.3] ₂ / 88.4] ₂ / -33.3] _s	15.7%	0.00%

Table 5. Unconstrained and Hygrothermally Stable Optimal Shear-twist Coupled Laminates

n	Unconstrained Stacking Sequence (°)	Hygrothermally Stable by Equation 1 (°)	% Reduction in Coupling compared to Unconstrained
2	[85.3 / 49.7]	N/A	N/A
3	[33.2 / -12.4 / -5.5]	N/A	N/A
4	[-35.2 / 30.4 / 87.9 / 3.0]	N/A	N/A
5	[-43.5 / 46.7 / 4.6 / 88.8 / 0.2]	[-36.2 / 33.9 / 67.5 / -78.9 / -8.8]	36%
6	[42.9 / -46.4 / -6.3 / -88.8 / 89.9 / 0.4]	[87.5 / 8.6 / 4.6 / -73.3 / -48.8 / 44.4]	7.9%
7	[-42.6 / 46.8 / 10.4 / 88.7 / 89.8 / -89.6 / -0.5]	[81.9 / 0.6 / 0.7 / 86.6 / -61.6 / -16.5 / 54.9]	14%
8	[40.8 / -48.8 / -21.2 / -89.7 / 89.9 / 89.8 / -0.1 / 0.6]	[42.2 / -15.7 / -44.2 / 86.5 / 86.4 / 2.1 / 85.7 / 1.6]	9.5%
9	[41.2 / -49.9 / -32.1 / 89.9 / 89.9 / 89.8 / 89.8 / 0.3 / 0.9]	[87.6 / 2.8 / 88.6 / -0.7 / -0.8 / 85.1 / -17.9 / -65.8 / 49.6]	5.9%
10	[34.4 / 46.0 / -47.6 / -23.9 / -8.9 / -89.3 / -89.7 / -1.0 / 89.9 / 0.5]	[86.8 / -0.1 / 1.3 / -88.9 / 0.6 / -88.6 / 83.7 / -8.7 / -46.1 / 43.5]	7.1%

Table 6. Unconstrained and Hygrothermally Stable Optimal Extension-bend Coupled Laminates

n	Unconstrained (°)	Hygrothermally Stable by Equation 1 (°)	% Reduction in Coupling compared to Unconstrained
2	[0 / 90]	N/A	N/A
3	[0 / 90] ₂	N/A	N/A
4	[0 / 90] ₃	N/A	N/A
5	[0 / 90] ₄	[59.6 / -34.9 / 86.2 / -29.9 / 25.6]	55%
6	[0 / 90] ₅	[89.1 / 1.1 / 30.7 / -46.5 / -54.6 / 47.8]	45%
7	[-17.3 / 18.6 / 88.5 / 87.6 / 87.3 / -86.7 / -83.5]	[79.8 / -30.8 / 17.7 / 44.0 / -45.9 / -46.5 / 53.9]	51%
8	[84.2 / 85.9 / -89.0 / -88.0 / -88.0 / -88.5 / -15.1 / 15.8]	[87.5 / 40.0 / -4.7 / -34.5 / -44.7 / 47.6 / -53.3 / 49.6]	45%
9	[20.6 / -4.5 / -37.6 / -89.7 / -88.8 / -84.6 / -86.2 / 84.7 / 82.9]	[80.4 / 52.8 / 5.4 / -16.3 / -39.8 / -51.3 / -53.3 / 49.7 / 48.6]	47%
10	[-83.0 / -84.6 / 87.7 / 86.6 / 86.5 / 88.4 / 88.9 / 27.4 / 1.3 / -22.7]	[68.0 / -71.7 / 6.6 / -10.9 / -38.9 / 44.7 / 5.0 / -50.1 / -51.8 / 50.5]	49%

Table 7. Unconstrained and Hygrothermally Stable Optimal Extension-bend Coupled Laminates, Orthogonal Axes

n	Unconstrained (°)	Hygrothermally Stable (°)	% Reduction in Coupling compared to Unconstrained
2	[85.3 / 49.7]	N/A	N/A
3	[44.4 / -47.8 / -14.6]	N/A	N/A
4	[84.0 / 18.9 / 44.3 / -45.3]	N/A	N/A
5	[80.7 / 21.0 / 43.5 / 45.7 / -46.5]	[74.2 / -49.1 / 14.0 / -40.4 / 46.0]	33%
6	[80.6 / 31.7 / 5.0 / 43.1 / 44.2 / -46.2]	[89.1 / 1.5 / 29.5 / -48.0 / -54.8 / 47.1]	8.3%
7	[79.7 / 32.0 / 11.9 / 42.9 / 44.2 / 44.7 / -47.3]	[79.8 / -31.1 / 17.8 / 44.1 / -44.8 / -47.1 / 54.0]	92%
8	[81.0 / 67.9 / 19.6 / -4.4 / 41.9 / -39.9 / -45.1 / 44.7]	[87.7 / 39.4 / -4.5 / -33.9 / -47.9 / 46.3 / -52.3 / 49.8]	17%
9	[80.3 / 69.5 / 22.4 / 5.0 / 41.2 / 43.2 / -42.0 / -46.1 / 44.9]	[77.2 / 11.8 / 59.4 / -22.8 / -40.3 / -45.5 / -48.8 / 49.2 / 47.8]	19%
10	[80.4 / 71.6 / 28.5 / 12.9 / -9.9 / 42.6 / 3.6 / -42.5 / -46.0 / 44.8]	[69.3 / -72.9 / 0.7 / -4.1 / -33.2 / 52.4 / -44.3 / 50.5 / 51.7 / -49.5]	21%

Table 8. Hygrothermally Stable Optimal Anticlastic Coupled Stacking Sequences

n	Equation 1 (°)	Equation 2 (°)
2	N/A	[-45] _s
3	N/A	[45 / -45] _s
4	[± 45] _s	[± 45] _s
5	[51.3 / -53.2 / -1] _s	[± 45 / -45] _s
6	[-48.2 / 49.2 / 0.1 / 89.9 / 40.8 / -41.8]	[45 / -45] _{2s}
7	[49.6 / -48.8 / -50.9 / -1 / 50.9 / 48.8 / -49.6]	[45 / -45] _{2 / 45]_{3 / -45]}}
8	[± 45 / (∓ 45) ₂ / ± 45]	[± 45 / (∓ 45) ₂ / ± 45]
9	[47.2 / -47.8 / -48.7 / 50.6 / 0 / -50.6 / 48.7 / 47.8 / -47.2]	[∓ 45 / ± 45 / 45 / ± 45 / ∓ 45]
10	[44.2 / -44.0 / -43.6 / 42.7 / 89.9 / -0.1 / -47.3 / 46.4 / 46.0 / -45.8]	[± 45 / ∓ 45 / 45] ₂ / ∓ 45 / ± 45]

Table 9. Unconstrained Optimal Anticlastic Coupled Laminates with Coupling Loss due to Hygrothermal Stability

n	Unconstrained (°)	Equation 1 Coupling Loss	Equation 2 Coupling Loss
2	[± 45]	N/A	33%
3	[45] ₂ / -45]	N/A	11%
4	[± 45] ₂	11%	11%
5	[± 45 / 45 / ± 45]	21%	7.1%
6	[45 / -45] ₂ / 45] ₂ / -45]	31%	2.5%
7	[45 / -45] ₂ / 45] ₃ / -45]	7.8%	0%
8	[± 45 / (∓ 45) ₂ / ± 45]	0%	0%
9	[∓ 45 / ± 45 / 45 / ± 45 / ∓ 45]	4.2%	0%
10	[± 45 / ∓ 45 / 45] ₂ / ∓ 45 / ± 45]	5.9%	0%